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Critical assessment of the scope and practical applicability of circularity indicators for sustainable wind turbine blade life cycle management

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INTRODUCTION

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- Wind energy sector is growing by **2050 the 15–18 %** of global electricity will be generated from this sector, increasing the demand up to **570 GW** [1]
- **Wind turbines** have a short operational **lifespan of 20-25 years** [2] , where especially the treatment of the **residual blades is a problem** because of the **composite materials** (difficult separation).

[1] S. Yousef, J. Eimontas, I. Stasiulaitiene, K. Zakarauskas, N. Striūgas, Recovery of energy and carbon fibre from wind turbine blades waste (carbon fibre/unsaturated polyester resin) using pyrolysis process and its life-cycle assessment, Environ Res (2023)

[2] J.M.F. Mendoza, D. Ibarra, Technology-enabled circular business models for the hybridisation of wind farms: Integrated wind and solar energy, power-to-gas and power-to-liquid systems, Sustain Prod Consum 36 (2023)

[3] B. Diez-Cañamero, J.M.F. Mendoza, Circular economy performance and carbon footprint of wind turbine blade waste management alternatives, Waste Management 164 (2023)

[4] M.Y. Khalid, Z.U. Arif, M. Hossain, R. Umer, Recycling of wind turbine blades through modern recycling technologies: A road to zero waste, Renewable Energy Focus 44 (2023)

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- **Wind turbine Blades (WTB)** design is based on the use of **glass and/or carbon reinforcement fibres**, a **thermoset-based polymer matrix** (e.g. epoxies), a **sandwich core** (e.g. balsa wood or foams), **coatings** (e.g. polyethylene or PU), and **metals** (e.g. copper wiring and steel bolts) [3].

Teng, H., Li, S., Cao, Z., Li, S., Li, C., & Ko, T. J. (2023). Carbon Fiber Composites for Large-Scale Wind Turbine Blades: Applicability Study and Comprehensive Evaluation in China. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 11(3). <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse11030624>

Skelton, K. (2017). *Discussion paper on managing composite blade waste*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22748.90248>

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- This **mix of materials makes** recycling **technically complex** because once thermoset composites are cured the polymers become **cross-linked**, undergoing an **irreversible separation process** [3].
- It is expected that **570 Mt of blade waste** will be generated in **Europe by 2030** [4]

[1] S. Yousef, J. Eimontas, I. Stasiulaitiene, K. Zakarauskas, N. Striugas, Recovery of energy and carbon fibre from wind turbine blades waste (carbon fibre/unsaturated polyester resin) using pyrolysis process and its life-cycle assessment, Environ Res (2023)

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INTRODUCTION

- Different WTB-EoL management alternatives:

- The management of the End-of-Life (EoL) of WTB represents a **critical global problem** [5] that should be **urgently handled**.
- There is a **lack of studies analysing the scope and applicability** of circularity metrics to determine the actual **circularity and environmental sustainability improvements** [6].

[5] Liu, P., Barlow, C.Y., Wind turbine blade waste in 2050. Waste Management 62, 229–240.(2017)

OBJECTIVE

OBJECTIVE

Qualitatively exploring the **applicability of circularity indicators** to assess **opportunities for sustainable life cycle management** of WTBs.
Identifying the need to develop more **realistic and useful indicators** for the **industrial sector**.

METHODOLOGY

METHODOLOGY

METHODOLOGY

1) Systematic literature review

METHODOLOGY

2) Characterization

Repurposing
Recycling (mechanical, chemical (pyrolysis) and
thermal (solvolysis))
Co-processing
Incineration
Landfill

Determination and characterization of **critical points** in relation to **inputs and outputs**.

Filtering indicator according to different checklist criteria:

- 1) Scientific relevance based on RACER methodology [7]
- 2) Circular design of composite products [9]
- 3) Circular economy frameworks developed for the wind industry [8]

Final sample of **scientifically relevant** indicators aligned with **circular composite design** and **wind industry criteria**.

3) Assessment of the scope and applicability of circularity indicators to analyze the performance of WTB-EoL management scenarios

[7] Author, R., & Bachmann, T. M. Critical evaluation of material criticality and product-related circularity approaches WP n° and title WP1-Concept and specifications ORIENTING -ecoinvent. (2024).

[8] Lobregt, M. Kamper, S. Besselink, J., Knoal, E. Coolen, E. The ideation process focused on circular strategies in the wind industry (2021).

[9] Joustra, J., Flipsen, B., & Balkenende, R. Circular design of composite products: A framework based on 280 insights from literature and industry. Sustainability (Switzerland), (2021)

RESULTS

RESULTS: WTB-EoL management alternatives

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Transformation wind blades into new products (furniture or playground components) [10]

✓ Extend life of WTBs

✗ Not all WTBs are suitable

RESULTS: WTB-EoL management alternatives

- **Mechanical:** Shredding and reuse of blade waste to build new materials [11]

✓ Recovery of other WTB materials (metals and balsa wood)

✗ Difficulty in marketing recycled materials (competition from virgin raw materials).

- **Chemical (pyrolysis):** Decomposition of the organic components of the blade by heat [12]

✓ Suitable for all types of waste, regardless of its quality

✗ Lower quality of recycled materials: Strength can reduce up to 50%

- **Thermal (solvolysis):** Dissolving part of the blade's components to separate the fibres from the rest of the components [13]

✓ Quality of recycled fibers comparable to virgin fibers: strength 58 % (GF), 95% (CF)

✗ Required chemical solvents can be environmentally hazardous

RESULTS: WTB-EoL management alternatives

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RESULTS: WTB-EoL management alternatives

Replace the content of virgin materials (sand or clay)
in cement production [14]

- ✓ Reduce CO₂ emissions of cement manufacturing by up to 16%
- ✗ Only suitable for GFRP-based blades

RESULTS: WTB-EoL management alternatives

Burning the blade once it has been dismantled and crushed [14]

- ✓ Reduce the volume of waste
- ✗ Release of harmful and hazardous gases

RESULTS: WTB-EoL management alternatives

Entire WTB disposal [14]

✓ Cheapest solution

✗ Not coherent with requirements of the CE
(banned in some EU countries)

RESULTS: WTB-EoL management alternatives

RESULTS: Circularity indicators

- Only **15%** of total indicators have passed corresponding filters

Circularity indicator	Variables	Life cycle stage	CE strategies
Material circularity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Circular inflow and outflows • Recovery potential • Actual recovery • Renewable or non-virgin content 	Raw material processing Product manufacturing Operation, maintenance and service Second life cycle loop	Narrowing/Slowing/Closing
Circular material use rate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Circular use of materials • Overall material use • Domestic material consumption • Amount of imported and exported waste bound for recovery • Imported and exported waste • Amount of imported and exported secondary material 	Raw material processing Dismantling and EoL management Second life cycle loop	Slowing/Closing
Material circularity indicator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mass of primary material resources contained in a product • Mass of unrecoverable waste generated at end-of-life • Product mass • Mass of unrecoverable waste associated with producing the recycled material contained in the product • Mass of unrecoverable waste when recycling parts of a product. • Product design life based on a market average • Actual lifetime and use intensity of the product 	Raw material processing Product manufacturing Operation, maintenance and service Dismantling and EoL management	Narrowing/Slowing/Closing
Product circularity indicator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mass of the final product • Fraction of reused components • Amount of recycled content of the produced feedstock • Waste from feedstock production • Waste from component production • Fractions of material losses that are recovered as useful recycled material and collected end-of-use products available for component reuse • Efficiency of the material separation • Efficiency of the recycling process used to produce the recycled feedstock 	Raw material processing Product manufacturing Operation, maintenance and service Dismantling and EoL management	Narrowing/Slowing/Closing
Recycling desirability index	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mass fraction of a material in a part that makes a product assembly • Mass of material in a product or component • Total product mass 	Product manufacturing Operation, maintenance and service Dismantling and EoL management	Narrowing/Slowing/Closing/ Regenerate resource flows

RESULTS: Assessment

Processes	Sub-processes	Flows		Material circularity	Circular Material Use rate (CMU)	Material Circularity Indicator (MCI)	Product Circularity Indicator (PCI)	Recycling desirability index (RDI)
		Inputs	Outputs					
Repurposing	Dismantling Cutting Shredding Transport Surface processing	Workers Logistics operations (time and costs) Fuel Water Energy	Emissions (transport) Emissions (decommissioning) Dust and water (cut) VOCs and solid waste (repurposing)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗
Co-processing	Dismantling Cutting Shredding Transport Cement kiln	Workers Logistics operations (time and costs) Water Fuel Energy	Emissions (transport) Emissions (decommissioning) Dust and water (cut) Cement clinker, dust and energy (co-processing)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗
Mechanical recycling	Dismantling Cutting Shredding Transport Grinding Sieving	Workers Logistics operations (time and costs) Fuel Water Energy	Emissions (transport) Emissions (decommissioning) Dust and water (cut) Recovered fibres (recycling)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Thermal recycling	Dismantling Cutting Shredding Transport Pyrolysis Sieving Washing Post-oxidation	Workers Logistics operations (time and costs) Fuel Water Energy N ₂	Emissions (transport) Emissions (decommissioning) Dust and water (cut) Oil and gas products (pyrolysis) Pure fibres (post-oxidation)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Chemical recycling	Dismantling Cutting Shredding Transport Solvolytic reaction	Workers Logistics operations (time and costs) Fuel Water Energy Solvents	Emissions (transport) Emissions (decommissioning) Dust and water (cut) Fiber (solvolytic) Resin and recovered solvents (recovery)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Incineration	Dismantling Cutting Shredding Transport Incineration	Workers Logistics operations (time and costs) Fuel Water Energy	Emissions (transport) Emissions (decommissioning) Dust and water (cut) Ash, CO ₂ and energy (incineration)	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗
Landfill	Dismantling Transport Disposal	Workers Logistics operations (time and costs) Fuel	Emissions (transport) Emissions (decommissioning) GHG impacts (landfill)	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗

RESULTS: Assessment

- **PCI [17]** indicator cover **all the alternatives**.
- **RDI [18]** only contemplates **recycling alternatives**.
- **Material circularity [19]** and **CMU [20]** apply to all scenarios **except incineration and landfill**: The indicators contemplate circularity variables.
- **Material circularity indicator [21]** does **not cover the incineration and landfill** processes because its variables do not adjust to the process flows.
- Indicators **only contemplate material flow variables** , **not of economic or social characteristics**, (not contemplate some phases as decommissioning logistics operations)
- They do **not contemplate the quality of the materials** (important for the recycling phase) and there are **no specific variables** that refer to the **quality or properties of the fibers**.

[17] Bracquené, E., Dewulf, W., & Duflou, J. R.. Measuring the performance of more circular complex product supply chains. Resources, Conservation and Recycling, (2020)

[18] Mohamed Sultan, A. A., Lou, E., & Mativenga, P. T. What should be recycled: An integrated model for product recycling desirability. Journal of Cleaner Production (2017)

[19] CIRCULAR TRANSITION INDICATORS V4.0 Metrics for business, by business. (2023).

[20] European Commission. Statistical Office of the European Union. Circular material use rate : calculation method (2018)

[21] Goddin, J., Marshall, K., Pereira, A., Design, G., Herrmann, S., Ds, S., Sam, J., Dupont, T., Krieger, C., Lenges, E., Ben, C., Pierce, J., Susan, E., Gispén, I.-J., Veenendaal, R., Per, I., Natureworks, S., Ford, L., Goodman, T., Cockburn, D. Ellen MacArthur Foundation Project 26m (in alphabetical order) (2019)

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

CONCLUSIONS

- **Scarcity of indicators** that are adapted to the different criteria established.
- **Need for specific indicators** for the **wind energy sector** and for **composite materials design**.
- Filtered indicators can **partially cover the flows** from dismantling to each alternative.
- **Lack of variables** that cover the **economic, social and/or quality aspects** involved in the process and making the analysis of these alternatives incomplete.
- The **most complete indicator** analyzed is the **PCI**.

FUTURE WORK

- Development of a **database of indicators** to serve as a **support tool** for the **wind energy sector**.
- **Development of specific circularity indicator for the wind sector:** Aspects such as transport, logistics or material quality (little contemplated by the current indicators) would need to be considered, as they are very important in managing blades.
- **Apply and analyze the new indicators** developed for their validation in the sector.

Eskerrik asko
Muchas gracias
Thank you

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